

When Sex becomes a Science: From *Kāma* to *Comma Sutra*
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Introduction¹

The *Kāmasūtra* is without exaggeration one of the most widely known texts from classical Indian Sanskrit literature. This has everything to do with its topic, sex, which it treats in great detail and with striking frankness. Thus, after an introductory chapter the *Kāmasūtra* comes straight to the point, presenting an elaborate treatment of the technical aspects of having sex, from the nail scratches the lovers make on each other's bodies and the cries and moans they utter, to the various sexual positions and, finally, the after-play. How a man may acquire a woman with whom to perform all these feats is relegated to the following chapters. The first translation in a western language dates from 1883, by Richard Francis Burton (1821-1890),² and was dedicated to "that small portion of the British public which takes enlightened interest in studying the manners and customs of the olden East". In other words, from the *Kāmasūtra* we would be able to learn how the ancient Indians did it. Furthermore, the very existence of a text about sex, in combination with the erotic sculpture decorating the walls of many an Indian temple, has established the notion that the ancient Indians were a licentious lot. As to the latter point, while I would like to leave the explanation of the meaning of the erotic scenes found on the temple walls to the art historian, the reach of the *Kāmasūtra* should not be exaggerated. The text was composed in Sanskrit, which was a learned language cultivated almost exclusively by brahmins, and until the appearance of Burton's English translation, the *Kāmasūtra* circulated in manuscript form among these same brahmins, who formed after all only a small portion of the total population. As to the first point, that we might learn from the *Kāmasūtra* how the ancient Indians did it, as far as I can judge, everything mentioned in the text is indeed doable. However, this does not mean that the text intended the readers to act accordingly or that

¹ In this article I have brought together most of what I have written so far on the *Kāmasūtra* before and after the appearance of my Dutch translation of this text in 2008 (Tieken 2008^a), that is, Tieken 2001, esp. pp. 73-80, 2008^b, 2012^a, 2012^b, 2017, 2024 and Khoroché and Tieken 2009. Unless specified otherwise, the translations of passages from the *Kāmasūtra* and *Arthaśāstra* are mine, those of the poems (*gāthās*) of the *Sattasāi* are Peter Khoroché's and mine.

² The edition appeared anonymously in the fictive town Cosmopoli. Though the translation is generally attributed to Burton, his contribution to it is actually marginal. The English text is held to be the result of the collaborative effort of Forster Fitzgerald Arbuthnot (1833-1901), Bhagvanlal Indrajī (1839-1888) and Sivaram Parashuram Bhīde. Unfortunately, for Bhīde no bio data are available. However, Madhav Deshpande, in an email dated 28-12-2017, drew my attention to the following publication by Pisanus Fraxi: *Catena Librorum Tacendorum: Being Notes Bio-, Biblio-, Icono-graphical and Critical, on Curious and Uncommon Books*, London: privately printed, 1885, where the author on pp. 458 ff. included an account furnished to him by Arbuthnot "of the way in which the translation [of the *Kāmasūtra*] was made, and of the difficulties attending it". The account dealing with the role of Bhīde reads as follows: "The copy of the text [of the *KS*] he [Bhagvanlal Indrajī] had procured in Bombay being incomplete, the pundit wrote for other copies from Calcutta, Benares and Jeypoor, and from these prepared a complete copy of the work. With the aid then of another Brahman by name Shivaram Par[a]shuram Bhīde, then studying at the University of Bombay, and well acquainted both with Sanscrit and English, and now employed in the service of His Highness the Guicowar [Gaekwad] at Baroda, a complete translation of the above text was prepared, and it is this translation which has now been printed and published in London, with the imprint of Benares, 1883". As Bhagvanlal Indrajī is said to be "unable to speak English fluently" we may assume that Burton's English translation is for the most part the work of this Bhīde, of whom we regrettably know so very little. Burton's contribution seems to have consisted mainly in adding footnotes elucidating certain curious Indian customs. As an example, I would like to quote the footnote concerning the so-called Gandharva marriage, or a marriage taking place without the consent of the parents: "This form of matrimony was recognized by the ancient Hindus, and is frequent in the books. It is a kind of Scotch Wedding – ultra Caledonian – taking place by mutual consent without any form of ceremony. The Gandharvas are heavenly minstrels of Indra's court who are supposed to be witnesses" (Burton 1883: 96).

they were used to do so of their own accord already. I am not referring here to those sexual positions which according to *Kāmasūtra* require exceptionally athletic bodies. Rather, I refer to the man who, when he has already tried everything else to have his way with a girl, plies her with alcohol and rapes her, or to one of the methods by which a man could enlarge the size of his penis, namely by having it stung by a bee or wasp. As to the latter method, no doubt it works, but I would not try it! To both cases, the rape and the bee sting, the warning may apply issued in *Kāmasūtra* 7.2.55 not to try out anything just because it is mentioned in a learned treatise. This raises the question with what kind of text we are dealing, going to such extremes as it does. While it cannot be denied that side by side to these criminal and painful methods the *Kāmasūtra* also provides useful suggestions on how to spice up one's sex life and that it is not impossible to derive from it information on the sex lives of the ancient Indians, I will try to show that it was not meant as either a handbook (Isidore Liseux [1925] describes the *Kāmasūtra* as a "manuel d'érotologie hindoue") or an ethnographic study (Schmidt [1922] "das Liebesleben des sanskritvolkes"). Instead, the text is in the first place concerned with mapping in great detail everything that might be relevant for people's sex lives; the so-called useful suggestions which are given, merely provide illustrations, and often only a selection at that, of the items or categories distinguished. Or, to put it more bluntly, the *Kāmasūtra* is not concerned with doing it, but with fantasizing about all the things one could, or might, do. This also raises the question what may have determined this particular approach to sex adopted in the *Kāmasūtra*. However, before going further into these questions I would like to draw attention to the systematic way in which its subject matter is treated in the *Kāmasūtra* and deal briefly with the prehistory of the text and the role attributed to Vātsyāyana, the author of the text, in bringing together related material of his predecessors in the field.

As for the structure of the text, the first chapter provides so-called introductory matter, beginning with a brief account of how the *Kāmasūtra* has reached its present form, which I will deal with below. This is followed by a veritable table of contents, a relatively new phenomenon in classical Indian literature. An earlier instance is found in Kauṭilya's *Arthaśāstra*. Next, we get a disposition on the place of *kāma*, or sexual pleasure, besides the other two aims in man's life, that is, *artha*, or taking care of one's livelihood, and *dharma*, or one's moral and social obligations; definitions of the terms used in the text, such as that of sexual pleasure; and a description of the ideal lover, or the *nāgaraka*. After this introduction, the *Kāmasūtra* comes straight to the point, with, in the second chapter, an elaborate treatment of the various sexual techniques. The next four chapters deal with the women involved, ranging from a young girl without any sexual experience, a faithful wife having

experience with one man only, her husband, and another man's wife (experience with two men, her husband and her lover), to, finally, the prostitute with many customers. The final, seventh, chapter deals with, among other things, aphrodisiacs and means by which a man could enlarge the size of his penis.

As indicated, the *Kāmasūtra* starts with an account of its prehistory. Originally it was the third, and final, part of a bulky text of as many as 100,000 chapters on the three aims of life, *dharma*, *artha* and, thus, *kāma*, composed by the Creator himself. The section on *kāma* was turned into a separate treatise of 1000 chapters, which was subsequently cut down in size to one of 500 chapters by Śvetaketu Auddālaki, and next to one of 150 chapters divided into seven parts by Bābhravya. After that, on the basis of these seven parts, seven separate treatises were said to be composed, the one covering the present first chapter of the *Kāmasūtra*, by a certain Cārāyaṇa, the part on sex, by Suvarṇanābha, that on virgins, by Ghoṭakamukha, that on wives, by Gonardīya, that on other men's wives, by Goṇikāputra, that on courtesans, by Dattaka and that on aphrodisiacs, by Kucumāra. Finally, these individual texts were brought together again by Vātsyāyana into the *Kāmasūtra* as we now have it. On several occasions the opinions of the authors of the seven earlier treatises as well as Śvetaketu Auddālaki and Bābhravya of the earlier abridgments, are quoted in the text, only to be overruled by Vātsyāyana, who has the final say in the matter. Unfortunately nothing more about this Vātsyāyana, or in full Vātsyāyana Mallanāga, is known than his name (Doniger 2002: xi-xii). However, at the end of this paper I will have occasion to come back to him. As to the date of the *Kāmasūtra*, the composition must be dated sometime between that of Kauṭilya's *Arthaśāstra* and Subandhu's *Vāsavadattā* since in 1.2.10 the text explicitly refers to the *Arthaśāstra*, and the *Kāmasūtra* is mentioned by name in the *Vāsavadattā*. Unfortunately, the exact date of the *Arthaśāstra* has not been established yet – it is anyhow older than the *Kāmasūtra*.³ The date available for the *Vāsavadattā*, which should furnish the *terminus ante quem*, is equally uncertain, ranging between the fifth and seventh centuries.

³ KS 1.2.10 refers to the second "book" of the *Arthaśāstra*, titled *adhyakṣapracāra*, "Activities of Superintendents". According to Olivelle, this text would have existed as an independent text before it had been

Lists and enumerations

As to the question of how the *Kāmasūtra* approaches sex, I will first have a closer look at a few of the many lists and enumerations found in it, starting with the list of the nail marks which the (male) lover makes on his (female) partner's body. Eight differently-shaped nail marks are listed, each with a suggestive name: the Gooseflesh, the Half-Moon, the Circle, the Line, the Tiger's Claw, the Peacock's Foot, the Hare's Leap and the Lotus Leaf. In addition six places on the body are mentioned where the marks are to be applied, followed by a categorization of the nails into long, short and medium (medium being the best as combining the qualities of both long and short). Then come detailed descriptions of the eight types of marks, which form an ascending scale on the basis of the visibility of the traces they leave on the woman's body. The first nail mark, called Gooseflesh, is also by far the most ingenious and imaginative of the eight (2.4.12):

Gooseflesh occurs when a man with well-trimmed nails lightly touches the woman's chin, breasts or lower lip, causing the hair on her body to rise. This does not leave any visible traces but afterwards, when the hairs lie down again and collide, they produce a soft, rustling sound.

However, on closer consideration, these eight types form only a selection out of an infinite number of varieties. Or, as the *Kāmasūtra* says (2.4.24):

People's imagination knows no bounds, their skills are infinitely varied, if they practice long enough they can learn anything, and in each and every case the result depends on the passion they put into the effort, So, scholars ask, who will be able to oversee all the possible forms of nail marks?

In this connection the number eight should be considered as well. As I have argued elsewhere (Tieken 2006: 453-5), in order to understand its meaning we should start from seven, which appears to be used almost universally – take our Seventh Heaven – to indicate the highest imaginable number. In India, for instance, memory goes back no further than seven generations (in genealogies), and one could also not think further ahead than seven generations (in curses). By adding one to seven, this limitation is as it were broken: one could, as in the case of the enumeration of the nail marks, easily go on much longer. However, the number eight should do – for the moment.

The section on the sexual positions – this enumeration does not stop at eight – ends in the same vein (2.6.41):

In the same way you may have sex as dogs do it, or goats or jackals, or you may assault a woman as donkeys do, play with her like a cat, jump on her like a tiger, crush her as if you are an elephant bull, rub against her like a boar or mount her like a stallion, or proceed in any other way not specified here.

What is meant is that one could easily add to the lists given or make other similar lists.

These examples show that the *Kāmasūtra* is actually about making lists of things and, apparently no less importantly, inventing apt and fancy names for them. In this connection I may refer to, for

incorporated into the *Arthaśāstra* (Olivelle 2013: 11). In dating the *Arthaśāstra* he distinguishes between the sources used by Kauṭilya, the original Kauṭilya composition and the subsequent so-called Śāstric Redaction. The *Kāmasūtra* would imitate the structure of this Śāstric redaction of the *Arthaśāstra*, which Olivelle places at around 300 A.D. For the date of the *Kāmasūtra* this results in the fourth-fifth centuries (Olivelle 2013: 25-31). It should be noted, though, that the existence of a *śāstric* redaction in the *Werdegang* of the transmission history of the *Arthaśāstra* is questionable (Tieken 2024). What this means for the date of the *Kāmasūtra* is, however, not yet clear.

instance, the sexual position called “Splitting the Bamboo”, in which the man places one of the women’s legs on his shoulder and presses the other one down on the bed, constantly changing the one for the other (2.6.28). This is how one splits bamboo.

The secondary nature of the concrete examples becomes even more clear in the sixth chapter on the prostitute. A considerable part of this chapter is, understandably, devoted to bookkeeping. It distinguishes profit and loss, additional effects and risks. First, these concepts are defined in terms of *dharma*, *artha* and *kāma*. Thus, there is profit and loss in terms of religious merit, wealth and pleasure. The same is done with the additional effects and risks. Risk may furthermore be divided into two types, namely whether actions will have an effect or no effect, or this effect or that effect. In addition to all these categories the *Kāmasūtra* distinguishes effects from two or more than two sides, depending on the number of the prostitute’s customers. After the financial system has thus been dissected into small fragments, everything is lumped together again. The result is a sheer endless number of combinations. However, only for a few of these, concrete examples are provided, for instance of profit that results in additional profit (when the woman has a lover of the highest class and as a result of which becomes sought after by other men; 6.6.13) and of profit without any additional profit (when she goes from one lover to the other of her own initiative; 6.6.14). These two examples concern additional effects in terms of financial matters. The section as a whole is concluded by the statement that “[t]he additional effects in terms of religious merit and pleasure can be calculated in the same way” (6.6. 19). Furthermore, Vātsyāyana also presents a discussion between two of his predecessors, Auddālaki and Bābhavya, about situations fitting the label “profit from two sides”, or when the prostitute has two customers. Auddālaki’s example is about a customer who is so fond of the prostitute that he is prepared to outbid every potential other customer (6.6.32). According to Bābhavya there is profit from two sides when the prostitute is entertaining a second paying customer and the first one is docile enough to continue paying her even while he is no longer welcome (6.6.36). What we see here is that the text starts from an exhaustive survey of theoretical possibilities and next leaves it to the reader to fill in the slots in the matrix with concrete situations which could serve as illustrations.

Another example of this approach is found in the beginning of the second chapter on sexual techniques. It is an interesting case as the approach is given a name there. The passage in question is about the selection of the ideal sexual partner, which is presented as a matter of physical compatibility. The text begins with distinguishing three criteria, namely the size of the partners’ sexual organs, the time they take to reach a climax and their temperament. To start with the size of the partners’ sexual organs, this ranges between small, average and large, resulting, according to the *Kāmasūtra*, in three equal combinations (small with small, average with average and large with large) and six unequal ones (small with large, etc.). For the two other criteria, time and temperaments, the same type of categories are made, resulting in altogether nine combinations of each, namely three equal and six unequal ones. This section is summed up as follows (2.1.33-4):

The forms sexual union can take when the nine of size are combined with the nine of time and the nine of temperament are too many to comprehend [729 to be precise]. But according to Vātsyāyana one should only start after having exactly determined (*tarkād*) one’s own position among all the possible combinations.

The keyword in Vātsyāyana’s closing remark is *tarka*. *tarka* is a science; it is an analytic method by which one may arrive at a proper knowledge or understanding of a complex situation. Thus, for good sex or to avoid disappointments one should beforehand thoroughly analyze the situation, in one’s mind going through all possible combinations in order to determine where one fits in. As in the above example, the analysis of *tarka* does indeed often involve high numbers or large quantities.⁴

⁴ For *tarka*, see also below. For the use of this word in a non-philosophical context, see Tieken and Sato 2000: 215-6.

A third variant of going from theoretical possibilities to concrete actions is found in the scenario for the wedding night, or rather wedding nights, in 3.2.1-28. This involves a young bride without any sexual experience. The first three nights after the marriage ceremony husband and wife sleep on the bare ground and refrain from sex, while eating food without salt and spices. During this time the husband should try to please the bride with small tokens of attention, for if he does not say a word, lying next to her “like a pillar”, she will be discouraged and think that she married to someone of the so-called third sex. On the other hand, he should never force her in any way, as women are as delicate as a flower. When taken by force, a woman will come to dislike anything to do with sex. A bride should not be conquered but be charmed.

He may embrace her gently but only her upper body and should immediately let her go again when he notices that she does not like it. If she has no previous experience, he should operate in the dark. Alternatively, he may light a lamp. He offers her betel, holding it between his lips and gently touching her lips with his. If she does not want to accept the betel in this way, he may even go so far as falling at her feet. For, as Vātsyāyana remarks, no woman is able to resist a man falling at her feet.

Next he should get the bride to talk and begin by asking her questions that can be answered by a simple yes or no. He may also enlist the help of one of his wife’s friends, one who is on his side. The friend may say things the bride does not want her husband to know and in this way elicit a reaction from her, like “I have never said anything like this”. Then he may ask his wife to tie a betel in the fold of his dhoti and while she is doing that touch her nipples with the Gooseflesh Scratch. If she stops him from doing that he should tell her that if she embraces him he will not do it again. And when she allows him to embrace her, he strokes her body as far as her navel. He takes her on his lap and goes further and further. When she tells him to stop, he blackmails her by telling her that he will scratch himself and tell everybody that it was she who did it. On the second and third nights he kisses her all over her body. Then, as if by accident he lets his hand fall between her thighs, loosening her waistband and putting aside her saree. He penetrates her and gives her sexual pleasure. But, the text concludes, he should not break the vow of chastity before the third night.

As in the examples discussed above, we are dealing here with just one of the possible scenarios for the wedding nights. However, the one described, which involves a young, innocent bride without any previous sexual experiences, is almost certainly the most elaborate scenario as it includes the various attempts on the part of the husband to overcome the bride’s shyness. The one involving a more streetwise wife would naturally be much shorter. In either case, for the lover it is necessary to find out exactly where in the path described he finds himself, on pain of making himself ridiculous. This is the point made in the *Sattasāī*, an anthology of erotic poems inspired by the *Kāmasūtra*. Take poem 767 of that anthology:

As soon as the husband took her on his lap
Sweat poured from her
Like an attendant servant,
Washing the mud of last night’s assignation
From her feet.⁵

The husband in this poem, in other words, need not have been so hesitant. In the following poem from the same collection, no. 684, the husband made a mistake in the opposite direction. He proceeded too hastily, starting to fumble at the knot in the bride’s saree while she was not yet ready for what would inevitably have followed:

⁵ The number 767 refers to Albrecht Weber’s 1881 edition of the *Sattasāī*. For the translation, see Khoroché and Tiekén 2009: 126, no. 403. See also *Sattasāī* 351: He was embarrassed/ But I laughed and gave him a hug/ When he groped for the knot/ Of my skirt and found it/ Already undone (Khoroché and Tiekén 2009: 59-60, no 158).

Feigning sleep
The husband turned over
And let a trembling hand fall as if by accident
On the knot of his young bride's skirt
Which she held firmly between her thighs.⁶

In these poems the *Sattasāi* reacts directly on the *Kāmasūtra*, in which everything imaginable is considered and treated as being equally relevant. The *Sattasāi*, by contrast, shows the futility of the lists and enumerations in this learned treatise, confronting the theory with the untidy reality of life. In the second poem of the *Sattasāi* this contrast is claimed to be one between *tantra*, or learned treatises, and *kāvya*, or poetry:

Shame on those who cannot appreciate
This ambrosial Prakrit poetry [*kāvya*]
But pore instead
Over treatises on love [*kāmatantra*].⁷

The *Kāmasūtra* itself is also quite modest about the usefulness of the above detailed surveys, lists and enumerations, or step-by-step plans like the one for the wedding nights. Thus, the section on slapping is concluded by several stanzas, including the following (2.7.31):

To what purpose all this counting and enumerating,
analyzing and dissecting?
Once lovemaking has got started,
The only thing that matters is passion.

Or take 2.2.31:

Books are for people in need of inspiration.
But once the wheel of sex is in full swing,
There is no need of books or manuals.

The ideal lover

Who would have been interested in imagining a detailed scenario for the wedding night(s) or making lists of nail marks and sexual positions, and inventing appropriate names for them, all activities with only very little direct usefulness? As I see it, the person the *Kāmasūtra* has in mind is the so-called *nāgaraka*, who is mentioned as one of the two sources of information on sexual relations, the other source being the *Kāmasūtra* itself (KS 1.2.13, for which passage, see below). By implication he is also the ideal lover, according to the criteria applied by the *Kāmasūtra*, that is. Interestingly, nothing is said about his looks. Instead, the *Kāmasūtra* provides a detailed description of the house he lives in and of how he spends his days. However, the first thing said about the *nāgaraka* is that he has mastered all sciences (*gṛhītaśāstra*) (1.4.1), obviously a reference to his period of studying with a *guru*. This means that he knows Sanskrit, the language in which the traditional sciences, including the *Kāmasūtra*, are transmitted. After his study, having become a “householder” (*gārhasthyam adhigamya*), he settles in a town (*nagara*), or any other place where there are “good people”

⁶ Khoroché and Tieken, 2009: 58, no. 149. In *Sattasāi* 723 the husband errs in the opposite direction again. The woman is sweating, which should have told him that she is already sexually aroused: Friend,/ I had to laugh/
When his hand fumbled at my thin skirt,/ Which stuck right to my sweating thighs (Khoroché and Tieken 2009: 58, no. 152).

⁷ Khoroché and Tieken 2009: 15, no. 2.

(*sajjana*), that is, people who, like him, live gentleman-like lives (1.4.2). The *nāgaraka*, whose name is derived from *nagara*, thus lives in a town and is a member of a cosmopolitan milieu. Next, we get a description of his house, which is situated near water and has an orchard, separate servant quarters and two bedrooms. It is furnished luxuriantly, with soft beds, mats on the floors, small tables with pots of beeswax, phials of perfume, pieces of bark from the lemon tree, betel leaves, and spittoons. On one of the walls hangs a lute; there is a board to draw or paint on, and a box of paintbrushes; books are lying around, and a board for chess and one for gambling. Outside there are cages for birds and a place for the *nāgaraka* to practice his hobbies, like carpentry. In the orchard there are benches to sit on in the shade and a swing.

After this (1.2.5 ff.) follows a description of how the *nāgaraka* passes his days – and nights. He starts his day by relieving himself, cleaning his teeth, and taking a bath. Every second day he rubs his skin with fragrant oils and he shaves himself every fourth. He takes his meals in the morning and afternoon and according to Cārāyaṇa, whom we know as the author of the original version of the first book, in the evening as well. After eating, he teaches his parrots and mynah birds to speak, goes to quail-fights, cock-fights and ram-fights, passes the time with friends and takes a nap. In the late afternoon he goes to a soirée to amuse himself. In the evening there is music and singing, and in his bedroom the *nāgaraka* and his companions receive women, whom they entertain with pleasant conversation and attentions.

Other occasions beside soirées at which the *nāgaraka* might amuse himself are festivals, drinking parties, picnics and group games. Each of these occasions is described in detail. Sticking to the soirée, or *goṣṭhī*, this is described as “a meeting of people who are each other’s equal in knowledge, intelligence, character and wealth taking place in the house of a prostitute, a hall otherwise used for assemblies, or just someone’s house, at which they sit relaxed and pass the time with pleasant conversations in the company of prostitutes, with thinking how a poem or any other work of art which had been left unfinished might be finished” (1.4.19-20).

As can be seen, in the description of how the *nāgaraka* spends his days any reference to work is missing. Apparently we are dealing with a member of the leisured class, a man who indeed has all the time of the world to give himself over to fantasizing about nail scratches, embraces, sexual positions, criteria determining the compatibility of sexual partners, reasons why one would seduce another man’s wife and whatever else plays a role in sexual relations. We are made to believe that this was how he and his like-minded companions spend their evenings. Doing so was fun, though the result was not always funny. For in making lists, after a certain point all the accepted methods have passed review and only the more outrageous ones are left. In fact, part of the fun may be to see how far one could go in producing ever new variants.

In this connection I should refer once more to verse 7.2.55, which reads that the fact that an unpleasant method is described in a learned treatise is no reason to put it into practice. Furthermore, I should add that the *nāgaraka* whose lists and scenarios tend to end in painful and absurd methods and situations is not a real person anyhow, at least not in the pure form in which he is described here. The *nāgaraka* is a mere invention by Vātsyāyana. The detailed analysis to which sexual pleasure is subjected in the *Kāmasūtra* simply requires a figure like him, a learned and rich man, who has the inclination as well as the time for such things. The approach to sexual relations chosen in the *Kāmasūtra* produced almost automatically the fictional character of the *nāgaraka*. If the approach was there first, what, then, may have determined it? In this connection I would like to refer to a few of the many points of close agreement that exist between Vātsyāyana’s *Kāmasūtra* and the *Arthaśāstra*, an earlier treatise on kingship already referred to above.

The relationship between the *Kāmasūtra* and *Arthaśāstra*

The indebtedness of the *Kāmasūtra* to the *Arthaśāstra* has been noted by many others before,⁸ and is evident at all textual levels, from vocabulary and arrangement to common types of lists and enumerations, and so-called discussions. In the following only a few of the more obvious features involved will be discussed, beginning with two structural ones. Thus, like the *Arthaśāstra*, the *Kāmasūtra* opens with a table of contents specifying the “books” (*adhikaraṇa*) and “topics” (*prakaraṇa*) to be treated. Both texts have an additional division into “chapters” (*adhyāya*).⁹ As far as we know, the *Arthaśāstra* was the first text in Indian literature with such a table of contents. The question of the originality of this three-fold division in the *Arthaśāstra*, into books, topics as well as chapters, has been discussed in great detail by Hartmut Scharfe (1993: 16-41), but need not concern us here, apart from Scharfe’s conclusion that Vātsyāyana seems to have been familiar with, and inspired by, this division of the *Arthaśāstra* (Scharfe 1993: 29). The other structural feature is that the *Kāmasūtra*, like the *Arthaśāstra*, ends with a chapter called “Secret practices” (*aupaniṣada*).¹⁰

In order to throw light on different aspects of a certain topic, like Kauṭilya, Vātsyāyana quotes the opinions of other scholars, scholars in general as well as individual scholars mentioned by the name. An example of the first type is found in AŚ 1.4.5-7, in which teachers of old (*ācāryas*) are quoted as saying that if a king wants to maintain order in the realm, he should be ever ready to use force (*daṇḍa*).¹¹ This method is subsequently rejected by Kauṭilya (“No, says Kauṭilya”), as in that way the king would only unduly frighten his subjects. At the same time, when reluctant to use force the king runs the risk of not being taken seriously, so instead he should use force in a just way. In some instances a third scholar is placed in between the anonymous scholars and Kauṭilya, as in the attempt to determine the number of the measures making up the king’s foreign policy in AŚ 7.1.2-5.¹² The teachers mention six such measures, namely peace, war, staying put, marching, seeking shelter and double-dealing.¹³ However, according to a certain Vātavyādhi these six measures can be reduced to two under the headings war and peace. The discussion is closed by Kauṭilya, according to whom we do have to distinguish six categories on the basis of the situations which trigger them. Vātavyādhi is one of a stereotyped set of seven scholars which we meet in passages like the one in AŚ 1.8.1-27 that deals with the question of who the king should appoint as ministers.¹⁴ The passage begins with the opinion of a certain Bhāradvāja, who suggests that the king appoints his fellow-students, for they enjoy his confidence. This suggestion is rejected by a certain Viśālākṣa, who argues that his former playmates would treat the king with disrespect, and that he should appoint his companions in vice instead. As he knows too much about them, they would not dare to offend him. The next authority, Parāśara, rejects this suggestion as well, for just as the king knows too much about his companions, they know too much about him, which may cause him to hesitate to reprove them should the occasion arise. Instead he should appoint men who have proved their loyalty by remaining at his side in critical circumstances at the risk of losing their own lives. According to the next authority quoted,

⁸ From Jacobi (1911) and Jolly (1915) in the beginning of the nineteenth century to Doniger (2016: 35 ff.) in the beginning of the twenty-first.

⁹ AŚ 1.2-18: *tasyāyaṃ prakaraṇādhikaraṇasamuddeśaḥ ... śāstrasamuddeśaḥ pañcadaśādhikaraṇāni sāsīti prakaraṇasataṃ sapañcāśad adhyāyaśataṃ ṣaṭ ślokaśahasrāṇīti*, KS 1.1.15-23: *tasyāyaṃ prakaraṇādhikaraṇasamuddeśaḥ ... evaṃ ṣaṭtriṃśad adhyāyāḥ catuḥṣaṣṭiḥ prakaraṇāni adhikaraṇāni sapta sapādaṃ ślokaśahasram iti śāstrasya saṃgrahaḥ*. Note that in both cases first books and topics are mentioned and only at the end, almost like an afterthought, the division into chapters is added.

¹⁰ In the *Arthaśāstra* the fourteenth *adhikaraṇa* is followed by yet another one on the so-called *tantrayuktis*. This final *adhikaraṇa*, however, “stands somewhat apart from the rest of the work, since it adds nothing to its subject matter, viz., the affairs of state, but refers to instead to the body of the work, discussing the presentation of its content” (Scharfe 1993: 266).

¹¹ See Wilhelm 1960: 79-80.

¹² Wilhelm 1960: 87.

¹³ On “double-dealing” (*dvaiddhībhāva*), see Botto 1972.

¹⁴ Wilhelm 1960: 5-11.

Piśuna, such devotion should not be mixed up with intellectual capacities. Piśuna's alternative solution is in its turn rejected by Kauṇapadanta, whose opinion is rejected by Vātavyādhi, while Vātavyādhi's suggestion is next rejected by Bāhudantīputra, according to whom the king should appoint men who are endowed with nobility of birth, intellect, integrity, bravery and loyalty. In this chain of opinions and their rejections Kauṭilya has the final say. According to him the individual suggestions offered are all equally valuable (*sarvam upapannam*), the choice between them depending on what is in the given situation required of the incumbent. In the *Arthaśāstra* these passages, which have become generally known by the term "polemics",¹⁵ may have different forms. In, for instance, the one concerning the vices (8.3.1-66) Kauṭilya rejects the opinions of each of these same seven authorities one by one.¹⁶ In this case there is no criticism of each authority by the following; and in the presentation of the Topic of Counsel (1.15.1-41) only the first four authorities are quoted.¹⁷

Like Kauṭilya, Vātsyāyana more than once makes use of such polemics. In, for instance, 1.3.34 he quotes the opinions of anonymous teachers (*ācāryas*), who are said to have claimed that it is useless to instruct women in the *Kāmasūtra* because women cannot deal with *śāstra*, or learned treatises. This opinion is, if not rejected, at least qualified by Vātsyāyana, who argues that even if women do not know the *śāstra*, they do know the practice taught in it, and this practice is dependent on learned texts: "This is so not only in the case of this particular *śāstra*. For all over the world there is only a handful of people who know the *śāstra*, while the practice [of it, or, the application of its principles] is within the grasp of many people".¹⁸ KS 6.6 is one long discussion between anonymous scholars and Vātsyāyana about different kinds of profits made by prostitutes. In this chapter seven pairs are found, each consisting of an opinion expressed by *ācāryas* and their subsequent rejection by Vātsyāyana. For instance, in 6.6.9-10 scholars are quoted as saying that between a lover who is in love and one who is generous, the obvious choice for the prostitute should be the generous one, an opinion rejected by Vātsyāyana on the ground that it is not impossible to turn a man in love into a generous one. As in the *Arthaśāstra*, inbetween the anonymous *ācāryas* and Vātsyāyana a third, named, scholar may be found, as in 5.6.39-42 which deals with men guarding the harem. According to the *ācāryas* such men should have passed the test of desire (*kāma*), or should be able to resist the temptation offered by the harem's inmates, while according to Goṅikāputra they should have passed altogether three tests, those of desire, fear(lessness) (*bhaya*) and incorruptibility (*artha*). The argument is concluded by Vātsyāyana who says that the guards should have passed the tests of *dharma* and *bhaya*, as a man with a strong moral character (*dharma*) will never betray his master and his fearlessness guarantees that he will under all circumstances stick to his moral principles.

As indicated above, Goṅikāputra is also the author of the text underlying the present version of the fifth book on other men's wives and in this capacity is thus quoted in his "own" book (5.1.8; 5.4.9). The other authors are found in similar roles. Thus, in the discussion on female orgasm (2.1.10-30) Vātsyāyana first cites the ideas of Auddālaki and Bābhavya, the authors of proto-*Kāmasūtras* mentioned above of 500 and 150 chapters respectively, after which he comes up with his own ideas. Suvarṇanābha is likewise quoted in his "own" second book on sexual techniques (e.g. 2.2.22; 2.4.6), Ghoṭakamukha in the third on the inexperienced virgin (3.1.3), Gonardīya in the fourth on the faithful wife (4.1.21; 4.2.34) and Dattaka in the sixth book about the prostitute (6.2.74; 6.3.44). Kucumāra, the author of the seventh book, is not mentioned anywhere else, while Cārāyaṇa of the first book appears only in combination with the others (see below). In KS 1.5.1 ff., as in AŚ 1.8.1-27 dealt with above, a whole string of these scholars are quoted in an enumeration of women who come into consideration as sexual partners. In the first instance the *Kāmasūtra* mentions three types of women: virgins, women getting a second chance (*punarbhū*) and prostitutes. To these three Goṅikāputra adds,

¹⁵ See the title of the book Friedrich Wilhelm published in 1960.

¹⁶ Wilhelm 1960: 35-41.

¹⁷ Wilhelm 1960: 11-18.

¹⁸ This passage is translated and discussed by Sheldon Pollock (1985: 507 ff.)

as may be expected of him given the topic of the book attributed to him, another man's wife. This is followed by an enumeration of altogether thirteen reasons why one should try to seduce such a woman.¹⁹ To these four women Cārāyaṇa adds a fifth, the widow; Suvarṇanābha a sixth, the female wandering ascetic; Ghoṭakamukha a seventh, a servant woman or the daughter of a prostitute who has not had a man before; and Gonardīya an eighth, a young woman of good family who is no longer a child. Like Kauṭilya in the *Arthaśāstra* discussions, Vātsyāyana claims the final say in this matter, arguing that the latter five women are included among the first three, because there is no difference in the purpose which they are made to serve.²⁰

These discussions in the *Arthaśāstra* between the *ācāryas* and Kauṭilya are examples of the way the king might arrive at a decision on how to act in a given situation. The approach is called *anvīkṣikī* in AŚ 1.2, or “investigating a situation/problem by weighing the arguments” (*anvīkṣikī ... hetubhir anvīkṣamāṇā*).²¹ However, similar to the way in which the *Sattasāi* makes short shrift of the usefulness of the scenario-making in the *Kāmasūtra*, the animal fables of the *Pañcatantra* do of that of the *anvīkṣikī* method of the *Arthaśāstra*. As shown by Ruprecht Geib (1969), the *Pañcatantra* is in many ways a spoof on the *Arthaśāstra*. An interesting example discussed by Geib (pp. 30-33) is how a former minister, the jackal Damanaka, manages to cause a rift between King Lion Piṅgalaka and the only faithful minister left to him, the bull Sañjīvaka, by producing an opinion put forward by Kauṭilya in AŚ 1.15.34-36 to conclude a discussion with Viśālākṣa, Parāśara and Piśuna on the number of ministers with whom a king should hold consultations: “The king should confer with three or four councillors, for with one only he may not come to any a decision in problematic cases, and a single minister behaves as he pleases as his opinions are not challenged”. Interestingly, the lion, an uncivilized animal from the forest, is less easily convinced by this argument drawn from a learned treatise than the bull scholar-minister, who immediately accepts the suggestion that the king might have come to distrust his advice. The point made is that the “theoretical” knowledge presented in the *Arthaśāstra* is useless in concrete situations in which different abilities are required, or, in the example under consideration, the ability to recognize the motive behind the jackal's meddling who was recently dismissed by the king and tried to settle an old score. In the *Pañcatantra* the important role of *anvīkṣikī* in the *Arthaśāstra* is taken over by *nīti*, or recognizing the true state of affairs. As shown by Albrecht Wezler (1993), similar discussions between, and with, teachers-scholars as found in the *Arthaśāstra* and *Kāmasūtra* are also found in the *Carakasamhitā*, a medical text. It is telling

¹⁹ KS 1.5. 8ff. It should be noted that at thirteen, the number of reasons is not yet exhausted. Only “political” considerations are mentioned, or how with another man's wife one could deal with one's enemies (for this point of view, see Doniger 2016: 62-63). In what follows a selection of two such considerations: “[A man] thinking ‘her husband is a great and powerful man and an ally of my enemies. However, at home he is at her beck and call. Once she has become intimate with me she will out of affection for me make him change his allegiance,’ ... or thinking ‘my enemy has made common cause with her husband, so I could use her to have a poisonous potion administered to him,’ ... For these and other such reasons one may decide to seduce another man's wife”. As a type, this passage has an exact counterpart in *Arthaśāstra* 7.1, in which, after the number of the measures of foreign policy has been fixed at six (see above), a long paragraph follows presenting altogether eleven considerations of why one may resort to a policy of peace. Again, a selection of two: “If one sees that by maintaining peaceful relations with one's enemy one's own undertakings will prosper greatly and those of the enemy will come to ruin ... or if one sees that by concluding the peace with the enemy one will cause a rift between him and his allies and bring his allies over to one's own side, ...if one sees that, to further one's cause one should opt for a policy of peace”. This is followed by similar lists for the other five measures.

²⁰ It should be noted, though, that in this case, in contrast to the *Arthaśāstra* passage summarized above, no reasons are supplied as to why or how the women fit into this category and the authorities do not react to each other's proposals. Another interesting case of such a “discussion” is found in KS 1.2.16ff. in which Vātsyāyana defends the existence of a treatise on sex against anonymous *ācāryas* who claim that “animals have sex without the help of books”, the pursuit of *dharma* against materialists, that of *artha* against fatalists and that of *kāma* against pragmatists.

²¹ As noted in the previous note, in KS 1.5.1 ff. the “reasons” are not specified. We seem to have to do with a superficial borrowing involving the form of a polemic, not the contents.

that in the latter treatise the discussions are referred to as *kathās*. At first sight the word *kathā*, or story, might not appear to be a very apt description of these discussions between learned men, discussions which, moreover, are said to aim at, and invariable end with, a *vinīścaya*, or a definite conclusion or decision.²² However, no matter how logical this decision may appear in the context of the discussion, we have seen that in concrete situations other factors have to be taken into account, and its usefulness is therefore restricted. This reduces the discussion itself to a noncommittal exchange of ideas between scholars unhampered by practical considerations or other urgent matters. It would thus seem that the word *kathā* describes exactly what the discussion is all about: a discussion following the logic of a story.

In fact, the same characterization may apply to practically every passage in the *Arthaśāstra*. Take for instance the long list of the so-called supervisors (*adhyakṣas*) making up the second book, *Adhyakṣapracāra*. The text mentions a supervisor for practically every activity in the realm imaginable. One cannot escape the impression that we are dealing with the outcome of a brainstorming session about the question what kind of supervisors one would need in a kingdom. The kingdom is built up from scratch. This results in a supervisor of yarns (*sūtrādhyakṣa*; AŚ 2.23) as well as one for mines (*ākarādhyakṣa*; AŚ 2.12) irrespective of the relevance of such supervisors for one's own realm. In this respect the lists in the *Arthaśāstra* do not differ from the lists and scenarios in the *Kāmasūtra*.

The science of sex

The points of agreement between the *Arthaśāstra* and *Kāmasūtra* dealt with above form only a random selection and can easily be multiplied. Considering the extent of the indebtedness of the *Kāmasūtra* to the *Arthaśāstra* it is tempting to ascribe to the author of the *Kāmasūtra* the intention to compose an *arthaśāstra* on sexual relations. Indeed, at the very beginning of the *Kāmasūtra*

²² Wezler quotes verse 7 of Chapter 26 of the *Sūtrasthāna*, which reads: *teṣāṃ tatropaviṣṭānām iyam arthavati kathā/ babhūvārthavidāṃ samyagrasāhāravinīścaye//* and to verses 3-7 of Chapter 25 of the same *sthāna*: *... prādurāsīd iyam kathā//3// ... sarva evāmitajñānavijñānacchinnasamśayāḥ/ bhavantaś chettum arhanti kāsīrājasya samśayam//7//* (Wezler 1993: 127 and 124-5 respectively).

Vātsyāyana made it clear that he intended to subject sexual pleasure to the same scientific approach as was *artha* in the *Arthaśāstra* (and *dharma* in the *Dharmaśāstra*). Immediately after the table of contents he identifies “his” *kāma* with the third of the traditional *puruṣārthas*, or aims in life, *dharma*, *artha* and *kāma*, and gives “his” *Kāmasūtra* a status comparable to the *dharma*- and *arthaśāstras*: what the *dharmaśāstras* – there are many of them – are for *dharma* and the *Arthaśāstra* – of which there is only one – is for *artha*, is his *Kāmasūtra* for *kāma*. First Vātsyāyana supplies definitions of *dharma* and *artha* and are we informed about what texts and which persons we should consult about matters of *dharma* and *artha*. *dharma* is said to cover actions like sacrifices, the results of which are invisible; they are not enjoyed in this life but only in heaven. For the rules of *dharma* one should consult the ancient scriptures on *dharma* and people who know everything there is to know about *dharma*; *artha* is concerned with the acquisition of the goods of life and for information one should read the *Arthaśāstra* and apprentice oneself to, for instance, a merchant. Next *kāma* is defined (1.2.11-12):

Pleasure (*kāma*) is the agreeable sensation which arises when each of the sense organs ear, skin, eye, tongue, and nose, under the supervision of Mind and Self, attaches itself to its own object. But pleasure (*kāma*) in the strict sense of the word is an experience of complete fulfilment, in particular through feeling with the skin, a fulfilment which is enhanced by the notion that such a sensation is essence of Man;²³

and (1.2.13):

Knowledge about *kāma* is obtained by studying the *Kāmasūtra* and seeking the company of the *nāgaraka*.

However, the original *kāma* of the three aims in life refers to the solemn duty to produce offspring which could perform the necessary ancestor rituals. In fact, the reader is hoodwinked here by the equation of the sexual extravaganzas of the *Kāmasūtra*, which are aimed at pleasure, with the cumbersome duty of producing offspring of the *puruṣārthas*.

Vātsyāyana makes this point at the very beginning of the text. How serious are we then to take the text that follows? Or what is the effect of the serious tone and learned vocabulary for dealing with a rather awkward subject like sexual pleasure and what are we to make of the *Kāmasūtra* as, but for the subject, an imitation of the *Arthaśāstra*? As to the first question, applying western standards – and the *Pañcatantra* and *Sattasāi* seem to show that the ancient Indian standards were not really different – we are dealing with a form of deadpan humor, marked by an affectation of seriousness and detachment. As to the second question, it is tempting to take the *Kāmasūtra* as a parody of, or a spoof on, the *Arthaśāstra*. In any case, who would have been able, once he had read the *Kāmasūtra*, to suppress a smile at the grave tone and learned arguments of the *Arthaśāstra*?

By way of conclusion I would like to briefly discuss two more points. The first concerns the identity of the author of the *Kāmasūtra*, Vātsyāyana, about whom, as indicated above, not much is known, and the second point has to do with the place of the text in Sanskrit literature. In my opinion it cannot be a coincidence that Vātsyāyana is also the name of the author responsible for introducing the term *anvīkṣikī* in Nyāya.²⁴ Though the term does not occur in the *Kāmasūtra*, the way in which sexual relations are investigated in that text, is in its model, the *Arthaśāstra*, called *anvīkṣikī*. The one time the *Kāmasūtra* attaches a name to its approach, it uses the word *tarka* (see above), which is yet another term from (and for) Nyāya. However, I do not think that the Nyāya scholar Vātsyāyana is the

²³ The terminology and the image of human experience in this definition have clearly been borrowed from Saṃkhya.

²⁴ See Paul Hacker’s detailed investigation of the term *anvīkṣikī* in the *Arthaśāstra* and Nyāya (Hacker 1958).

author of the *Kāmasūtra*. Rather it seems that we have to do with a *nom de plume*, adopted to make an indirect reference to the *Arthaśāstra* and at the same time adding to the pretense of providing a learned treatise.

As argued above, the *Kāmasūtra* was in the first instance taken as an ethnographic source on the sex lives of the ancient Indians. A similar claim underlies Richard Schmidt's *Beiträge zur Indischen Erotik* (1922), which deals with the *Kāmasūtra* and later treatises on *kāma*, and is subtitled *Das Liebesleben des Sanskritvolkes*. As such, the *Kāmasūtra* has drawn the attention of psychologists, as is shown by my own second-hand copy of Schmidt's *Beiträge*, which originally belonged to the Psychologisches Institut der Universität des Saarlandes. Thus, when Wendy Doniger in publishing her English translation of the *Kāmasūtra* in 2002 sought the collaboration of the psychiatrist Sudhir Kakar she stands in a hallowed tradition. However, as I see it, a more proper appreciation of the *Kāmasūtra* is to be found among the authors of the many modern comic versions of the text, such as the *Cosmo Kamasutra*, which offers "12 brand-new mattress-quaking sex styles", each with its numerical "degree of difficulty", including positions called 'the backstairs boogie', 'the octopus', 'the 'mermaid', 'the spider web' and 'the rock'n'roll (Doniger 2002: lx). An even more interesting example, perhaps, is the *Comma Sutra. Position Yourself for Success with Good Grammar* by Laurie Rozakis, Ph.D. [sic], in which one scientific field (that of the study of English usage guides) is mixed with the other (on sexual relations) and which includes chapters bearing titles like "Spice Up Your Life: Use Modifiers".²⁵ Furthermore, when the *Kāmasūtra* is indeed a parody or a satire of scholarly literature we should remove it from the category of scientific works, in which it was placed by, for instance, Moriz Winternitz (1985: 658-662) and situate it once and for all among that of *Kāvya*, or experimental belletré.

²⁵ Usage guides are generally marked by a lot of finger-wagging – when it comes to language not a few people evince a tendency towards masochism and like to be corrected (Pullam 2018). The detailed treatment and schoolmasterly tone, intended or perceived, of the usage guides is indeed an easy target for parody. I am grateful to my wife Ingrid for the reference to Pullam's article, which has appeared in a book edited by her.

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